

Probable dates and scenario of introduction of *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* in France

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Xylella fastidiosa was detected for the first time in the French territory in 2015, in Corsica and PACA regions. Most samples were infected by strains from two lineages (ST6 and ST7) of *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex*. While numerous of foci were detected all over Corsica, in natural, urban and semi-urban environments, in a large range of hosts (39 plant species), a more limited number of mostly urban foci was reported from PACA in a range of 25 plant species, from which 15 were not reported infected in Corsica. Hence, situations look like having different histories. Our aim was to decipher the most probable scenario of introduction of each ST in these two regions. A collection of 82 genome sequences including 56 genome sequences of French strains was used to date the divergence of French *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* strains from their American relatives. We developed a 13-VNTR scheme for direct typing of *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* in infected plant samples and used Approximated Bayesian Computation analyses to select the best scenario to explain the spread of the bacterium in France. The scenario choice and testing will be presented together with parameters allowing the selection of the best scenario and its interpretation in the context of plant trade.